

HIGH- AND LOW-CYCLE TENSILE FATIGUE OF ALL-CARBON HYBRID QUASI-ISOTROPIC LAMINATE

V. Carvelli ¹, S. B. Sapozhnikov ², S. V. Lomov ³ & Y. Swolfs ³

Is the pseudo-ductile quasi-static tensile behaviour of all-carbon hybrid composites retained under fatigue loading? This paper addresses this question by examining the low-cycle tensile-tensile fatigue behaviour of a unidirectional carbon laminate and the high-cycle fatigue behaviour of an all-carbon fibre hybrid quasi-isotropic laminate. The low-cycle fatigue, monitored with the acoustic emission recordings, indicates that the damage pattern observed during the first cycle is maintained in subsequent cycles, albeit with reduced intensity than the initial damage. The high-cycle tensile-tensile fatigue performance of an all-carbon fibre hybrid quasi-isotropic laminate revealed that its load-carrying ability is retained for load levels below the pseudo-ductile regime, while it is not beyond the limit of elastic response. Conversely, the all-carbon hybrid composite maintains its load-carrying ability during strain-controlled fatigue in the pseudo-ductile regime, albeit with a lower stiffness.

Keywords: Hybrid composites, pseudo-ductility, low-cycle fatigue, high-cycle fatigue

INTRODUCTION

Fibre-hybridisation can generate synergistic or ‘hybrid’ effects in fibre-reinforced polymer composites. Such effects can yield either better-than-expected properties according to the rule of mixture or properties that are absent in the constituent materials. The most important hybrid effect is pseudo-ductility, which occurs when combining brittle composites to produce a pseudo-ductile response, Czel and Wisnom [1] and Swolfs et al. [2]. It is often coupled to ply fragmentation, which allows the brittle ply to fracture multiple times and gradually transfer its load to the remaining ductile plies.

The quasi-static tensile failure of fibre-hybrid composites is well-understood. This leads to the design of “safe failure” materials and structures that keep their load-carrying ability after failure, allowing safe aborting of the dangerous performance scenario. Such a behaviour is also highly desirable for fatigue loading, although the current understanding of fatigue loading is more limited.

Fernando et al. [3], Dickson et al. [4] and Wu et al. [5] have reported that fibre-hybridisation can considerably enhance the tension-tension fatigue resistance. This effect is mainly due to the ductile fibres experiencing fatigue damage only at higher strain levels, which helps to stabilise the fatigue damage development in the brittle fibres or plies. This has also been described by computational modelling of the fatigue in hybrid composites, Dai and Mishnaevsky [6].

¹ Department A.B.C., Politecnico di Milano, Milan, Italy

² Aerospace Department, South Ural State University, Chelyabinsk, Russia

³ Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

Suwarta et al. [7] analysed the fatigue response of pseudo-ductile carbon/glass hybrid laminates concerning "safe failure" options. The response depended strongly on whether they were fatigued before or after the first ply fracture, and the fatigue life deteriorated strongly if the load exceeded this limit. Ribeiro et al. [8] examined the high- and low-cycle tension-tension fatigue response of carbon/glass fibre unidirectional hybrid laminates. The study focused on the maximum fatigue stress over the knee point, starting at the level of the pseudo-ductile plateau and up to the ultimate tensile strength of the hybrid composite. The stress-controlled fatigue showed a low fatigue life for the chosen range of loading conditions.

Multi-axial pseudo-ductile hybrid composites have not been studied for fatigue. Additionally, differences between the stress- and strain-controlled loading regimes have not been investigated. This work focuses on these two aspects, with the main question: can the pseudo-ductile quasi-static tensile behaviour of a hybrid composite be retained under fatigue loading?

MATERIALS

All-carbon fibre-reinforced hybrid composites are gaining much interest as promising pseudo-ductile materials for manufacturing lightweight components.

The present study investigated a laminate manufactured with two unidirectional carbon fibre prepregs supplied by Composite Materials Italy (CIT) – Toray Group, which both had the epoxy matrix ER450. The prepregs nominal fibre volume fraction was 55–56%. The prepregs used for the low-elongation (LE) and high-elongation (HE) components of the all-carbon hybrid laminate were the same as those employed in previous studies of the quasi-static behaviour of UD all-carbon hybrids [9, 10]. The high difference between the LE and HE stiffness and failure strain (see TABLE 1 for the main fibre properties) amplifies the hybrid effects, as demonstrated in Sapozhnikov et al. [9, 10]. The combination of the prepreg layer thickness and the interlayer toughness results in a well-defined pseudo-ductile plateau during quasi-static tensile loading. The hybrid composites investigated in this study have been previously studied by the authors in Sapozhnikov et al [9-11] and Carvelli et al [12, 13].

TABLE 1. Carbon fibre properties (obtained from manufacturer's data sheets)

ID	Fibre	Average diameter (μm)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Strength (MPa)	Failure strain (%)
T	TORAYCA® T700	5	294	5880	2
D	DIALEAD™ K63720	11	630	2620	0.4

The HE layer (thickness of 0.11 mm) was produced using the prepreg containing TORAY TORAYCA® T800 carbon fibres (hereafter referred to as T). The LE layer (thickness of 0.22 mm) was produced using the prepreg containing Mitsubishi Chemical DIALEAD™ K63720 carbon fibres (hereafter referred to as D). FIGURE 1a shows the laminate cross-section. The laminate consisted of a set of sub-laminates. The sub-laminate had one ply of the D prepreg sandwiched between two plies of T (T/D/T). Sub-laminates were stacked to create a quasi-isotropic layup [0/45/90/-45]_s. The laminates were cured in an autoclave for 2 hours at a 4.5 bar pressure and a temperature of 135 °C.

QUASI-STATIC TENSILE BEHAVIOUR

The pseudo-ductile tensile behaviour of the considered quasi-isotropic all-carbon hybrid laminate has three characteristic regions in the stress-strain diagram [9, 13], as illustrated in FIGURE 1b. The first region (LE/HE-stage) has an almost linear trend exhibiting a slope E_0 (72.8 ± 2.9 GPa) that combines the stiffness of the LE and HE layers. The limit of proportionality (ϵ_{PY}) indicates fracture of 0° LE ply. The pseudo-ductile plateau (PD-stage) with an almost constant stress level represents the second region. It starts at the pseudo-yield strain ϵ_{PY} ($0.41\% \pm 0.063$), very close to the ultimate strain of the LE component (TABLE 1). The plateau results from the onset of 0° LE ply fracture and propagation of the LE/HE interface delamination, as discussed in [9]. The PD-stage ends at the strain level ϵ_{EPY} ($1.15\% \pm 0.088$). In the third region (HE-stage), the laminate has an almost linear mechanical behaviour, whose slope E_I (15.3 ± 3.1 GPa) combines the stiffness of the intact 0° HE plies and the residual stiffness of the damaged LE ones (in the case of incomplete delamination).

FIGURE 1: All-carbon hybrid laminates: (a) structure of the laminate; (b) a typical quasi-static tensile diagram

LOW CYCLE FATIGUE OF UD PLYS

As a preliminary step, the damage imparted in a UD laminate during low-cycle fatigue was studied to assess whether the repeating load changes the damage pattern in the first fatigue cycle.

Relatively low strain rates during low-cycle and ultra-low-cycle fatigue allow the use of traditional quasi-static models for analysing the state of composites, Sapozhnikov et al. [14]. As an example of this analysis, this section presents loading diagram of the first 50 cycles (FIGURE 2a) of a unidirectional six plies prepreg DIALEAD™ K63720/ER450 [D6]. The stress-controlled test with a maximum stress level equal to 75% of the material strength has demonstrated slight hardening and cyclic creep (one-way accumulation of strains), as shown in FIGURE 2b. The accumulation of strain can be explained by the fact that CFRP is not ideally

unidirectional. This is confirmed by μ CT data (Nanotom GE) on a hybrid CFRP T700/DIALEAD/T700 ($T_2/D/T_2$), [9], see FIGURE 3.

FIGURE 2: 50 cycles of tension-tension loading of a $[D_8]$ specimen: (a) stress vs. strain diagram; (b) strain vs. time diagram.

FIGURE 3: Misorientations of fibres in UD plies: (a) μ CT- image of hybrid UD composite T_2DT_2 ; (b) misalignment angles for T800 and DIALEAD fibres.

Over 50 cycles, the strain of the unidirectional laminate $[D_8]$ increased by 8%, from 0.3% to 0.325%. We believe this is because the misaligned fibres have mostly realigned as creep has ceased (FIGURE 2b).

The analysis of the acoustic emission event parameters (in particular, the energy and the peak amplitude) indicated that the main fraction of events occurs in the first half-cycle, see FIGURE 4. These events continue to occur during subsequent cycles and even during unloading. Therefore, the Kaiser effect is not observed.

FIGURE 4: AE registration of the first cycles of repeated tension loading, [D₈] specimen: (a) energy and (b) maximum frequency amplitude of AE events.

Among the acoustic events, there are repeating groups with the same maximum frequencies $F_{\max}$: 100 – 200 kHz, 350 – 550 kHz, and (less pronounced) 950 – 1300 kHz. It suggests that the unidirectional composite experiences frictional events with varying frequency ranges during tension, which could be linked to fibre-matrix interface friction for fibres with different curvatures.

It is difficult to definitively establish a correlation between the frequencies of acoustic events and the angles of curvature of the fibres. But a possible explanation could be the appearance in the first half-cycle of low-frequency events linked to debonding in the most curved fibre, then mid-frequency events in fibres with less curvature, and, finally, the high-frequency events (950-1300 kHz). This may result from the failure of the straightest fibres, as events of this nature were scarcely observed during unloading and repeated loading. Only events in the 350

- 550 kHz range were repeated, which may occur due to sliding at the fibre-matrix interfaces during unloading.

HIGH CYCLE FATIGUE

Two sets of rectangular specimens of quasi-isotropic all-carbon hybrid laminates have been used in stress- and strain-controlled high-cycle fatigue tensile-tensile tests along the 0° fibre direction. The results of those tests have been previously reported in [12].

Stress-controlled high-cycle tension-tension fatigue

Fatigue stress-controlled tests were performed with a constant stress amplitude, sinusoidal wave-form tensile-tensile loading. A ratio $R = 0.1$ (ratio of the minimum to the maximum stress in the cycle) and a frequency of 5 Hz were imposed. The stress was estimated using the cross-sectional area of the pristine specimens. Three ratios of the maximum stress in the cycle and the quasi-static pseudo-yield stress σ_{PY} (almost 298 ± 17 MPa, FIGURE 1b) were considered. The test was performed until complete failure or run-out after 1 million cycles.

The maximum stress levels in the cycle were selected within the LE/HE-stage of the quasi-static diagram (FIGURE 1b): 90%, 95% and 100% of σ_{PY} . The fatigue life of the hybrid laminate for each stress level (at least three specimens) is presented in the diagram of FIGURE 5a.

FIGURE 5: High-cycle fatigue tests under stress control: (a) max stress vs. number of cycles curve, (b) stiffness retention with number of cycles.

The complete failure did not occur before one million cycles with the maximum stress of 90% of the quasi-static stress σ_{PY} . Increasing the stress level in the cycle, the average fatigue life was about 62,000 and 700 cycles for stress levels of 95% and 100%, respectively. This demonstrates that, for the stress-controlled loading, the laminate cannot sustain cyclic loading at a stress level above σ_{PY} (FIGURE 5a). This can be explained by the failure of the 0° LE plies at the stress level σ_{PY} , followed by the fast propagation of the damage during subsequent cycles at the same constant maximum stress.

FIGURE 5b shows the stiffness retention under stress-controlled fatigue. The stiffness is calculated as the slope of the line passing through the maximum and minimum of the stress-strain cycle, and the stiffness retention is defined as the stiffness at the i -th cycle divided by the stiffness of the tenth cycle. The stiffness remained almost constant up to 10^4 cycles for both 90% and 95% stress levels. However, for the 90% stress level, the stiffness had a slight reduction up to run-out of approximately 5%, while the damage spreads rapidly for the 95% stress level, resulting in failure after an abrupt drop in stiffness (FIGURE 5b).

The evolution of stiffness during cyclic loading with a peak stress of 100% σ_{PY} shows three distinct stages (FIGURE 5b). A continuous linear degradation of the stiffness, in the initial stage, which can be attributed to the fracture of the 0° LE plies and an increase of the transverse cracks in $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies. The stiffness of the composite had a slight decrease, in the second stage, which may be connected to the spread of intra-sub-laminate- and inter-sub-laminate delamination at the $0^\circ/45^\circ$ and $\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ$ interfaces. A sudden drop of the stiffness characterises the third and final stage, probably attributed to the fracture of the 0° HE plies, leading to failure after a few tens of cycles.

Strain-controlled high-cycle fatigue

The strain-controlled fatigue tests had a sinusoidal waveform with a ratio $R = 0.1$ (ratio of the minimum to the maximum strain in the cycle) and a frequency of 5 Hz. The distance between end tabs (140 mm) was adopted as the base length to estimate the strain. Several levels of the maximum strain in the cycle have been chosen above the pseudo-yield strain ε_{PY} level (FIGURE 6a). The specimens underwent cyclic loading until they either failed completely or reached run-out after 1 million cycles.

FIGURE 6: High cycle fatigue tests under strain control: (a) fatigue tests stress/strain levels compared to quasi-static behaviour, initial fatigue stress/strain level, residual stress after 1 million cycles (run-out), (b) stiffness retention with the number of cycles for some strain levels.

Eight different maximum strain levels, ranging from 0.46% - 1.7%, have been selected to cover both the quasi-static pseudo-ductility (PD-stage) and high elongation (HE-stage) behaviour of the hybrid laminate (see FIGURE 6a).

All fatigue specimens survived 1 million cycles, except for the one subjected to the highest strain level (1.7%), with a fatigue life of approximately 909,000 cycles.

During strain-controlled cyclic loading, the delamination created by the first loading cycle is extended with subsequent cycles. The residual fatigue maximum stress may be considered the macroscopic evidence of a similar damage pattern for all fatigue strain levels in the PD-stage (FIGURE 6a). The residual stress levels are aligned along a line with a slope which is almost the same as the one of the quasi-static tensile HE-stage, where the load is mainly carried by the 0° HE plies.

For the strain levels in the quasi-static HE-stage (>1.2% in FIGURE 6a), the initial damage patterns resulted in negligible coupling between the damaged LE and HE plies. The fatigue endurance was mainly transferred to the 0° HE plies, which were gradually damaged during cyclic loading. This led to a reduction in the residual stress as the applied cyclic strain level increased (FIGURE 6a).

FIGURE 7: Damage modes during the fatigue loading: (a) XCT-registered damage, strain control test, strain level 0.46%, after 100,000 cycles; (b) edge photograph of a laminate, strain control test, strain level 1.0%, 1 million cycles

The stiffness retention highlights the evolution of the damage with the number of cycles. The stiffness retention shows a considerable initial drop (see FIGURE 6b), which varies according to the strain level, limited to the initial 100,000 cycles. Subsequent cyclic loading resulted in a slight reduction of the stiffness. The initial drop for strain levels within the PD-stage (from 0.8% to 1.21%) is mainly attributed to the development of the intra- and inter-sub-

laminates delamination (see Figure 7b). This results in a residual stress state belonging to the HE-stage linear behaviour of slope E_I (FIGURE 6a).

The fatigue loading with the lower strain level of 0.46%, close to ε_p , resulted in an initial reduction of stiffness mainly due to the initiation of delamination and transverse cracks in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° plies, as illustrated in Figure 7a. Further cyclic loading caused a slow delamination propagation at different interfaces through the thickness leading to a continuous slight reduction of the stiffness (FIGURE 6b).

CONCLUSIONS

The tension-tension fatigue behaviour of an all-carbon hybrid quasi-isotropic laminate has been studied to assess the effect of the laminate pseudo-ductile behaviour on fatigue performance. Preliminary low-cycle tension-tension fatigue loading of UD plies showed that the main damage is imposed in the first load cycle, if the cyclic load level is below the strength of the LE ply. High-cycle stress-controlled tension-tension fatigue does not preserve the quasi-ductile nature of the laminates, characteristic of the quasi-static loading. The laminate loses its load-carrying ability when the fatigue maximum stress reaches pseudo-yield stress, which corresponding to the failure of LE plies. Contrary to that, the composite retains its load-carrying ability in the pseudo-ductile regime under strain-controlled tension-tension fatigue, albeit with decreased stiffness.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work of S. B. Sapozhnikov was supported by the Russian Science Foundation (project No.23-19-20039) and partially by KU Leuven.

LIST OF SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

E_0, E_I	Young's moduli of the composite, initial and after the pseudo-ductile plateau
LE, HE	Low elongation and high elongation fibres
$\varepsilon_{PY}, \varepsilon_{EPY}$	Pseudo-yield strain and strain at the end of the pseudo-ductile plateau
σ_{PY}	Pseudo-yield stress

REFERENCES

- (1) Czel, G. and M.R. Wisnom, *Comp Part A*, Vol. 52, 2013, pp. 23–30.
- (2) Swolfs, Y., I. Verpoest, and L. Gorbatikh, *Int Materi Rev*, Vol. 64, 2019: 181–215.
- (3) Fernando, G., R.F. Dickson, T. Adam, H. Reiter, and B. Harris, *J Mater Sci*, Vol 23, 1988, pp. 3732–3743.
- (4) Dickson, R.F., G. Fernando, T. Adam, H. Reiter, and B. Harris, Fatigue behaviour of hybrid composites. *J Mater Sci*, Vol 24, 1989, pp. 227–233.
- (5) Wu, Z., X. Wang, K. Iwashita, T. Sasaki, and Y. Hamaguchi, *Comp Part B*, Vol 41, 2010, pp. 396–402.
- (6) Dai, G. and L. Mishnaevsky Jr, *Comp Sci Techn*, Vol. 94, 2014, pp. 71–79
- (7) Suwarta, P., M. Fotouhi, G. Czél, M. Longana, and M.R. Wisnom, *Comp Struct*, Vol. 224, 2019, p. 110996.

- (8) Ribeiro, F., J. Sena-Cruz, and A.P. Vassilopoulos, *Int J Fatigue*, Vol. 146, 2021, p. 106143.
- (9) Sapozhnikov, S.B., Y. Swolfs, and S.V. Lomov, *Comp Struct*, Vol. 236, 2020, p. 111886.
- (10) Sapozhnikov, S.B., Y. Swolfs, and S.V. Lomov, *Comp Part B*, Vol. 198, 2020, p. 108213.
- (11) Sapozhnikov, S.B., Y. Swolfs, and S.V. Lomov, *Comp Struct*, Vol. 269, 2021, p. 114053.
- (12) Carvelli, V., S.V. Lomov, S.B. Sapozhnikov, C. Breite, and Y. Swolfs, *Phil Trans Royal Soc A*, Vol. 381, 2022, p. 20210222.
- (13) Sapozhnikov, S.B., S.V. Lomov, Y. Swolfs, and V. Carvelli, *Comp Part B*, Vol. 237, 2022, p. 109870.
- (14) Sapozhnikov, S.B., M.V. Zhikharev, and E.M. Zubova, *Comp Struct*, Vol. 286, 2022, p. 115293.